

**Unpacking the Dynamics: A Qualitative Investigation of Contemporary Hooligan Culture
and Reappearing Hooligan Violence in English Football.**

Undergraduate Dissertation

Abstract

Hooliganism and hooligan violence are phenomena discussed profoundly in contemporary discourse yet remains rarely comprehended. The substantive rise in hooligan violence provided the impetus for the examination launched by this dissertation. Hooligans are regularly depicted as evoking attributes of drunkenness, aggressiveness and modelling a contemporary threat to society. This dissertation maintains that such negative narratives obstruct societal understanding of hooliganism and hinders practical policing strategies to maintain football violence. This dissertation adopted a qualitative framework, utilising 6 semi-structured interviews to extract a valuable narrative of hooliganism and hooligan violence through a hooligan's perspective. Football hooligans from Manchester United, Birmingham City, Leicester City, West Ham and Millwall were included due to their prevalence for banning orders in the 2022-2023 season. Hooligans regarded various interconnected themes in influencing hooliganism and football violence. For instance, themes covered group-bonding, masculine working-class origins, football team alliance and anti-policing ideologies. Firstly, belonging interconnected passions for social solidarity and heightened violence to protect their newly founded social collective. Secondly, the masculine working-class heritage cultivates a culture of quasi-violence, integrating violence alongside the advancement of collective identity and social hierarchy. However, unlike scholarly literature, hooligans disregarded enduring inadequate and negative upbringings. Thirdly, team alliance facilitates territorial attitudes, breeding robust bonds between hooligans and nurtures significant hatred towards rivals. Lastly, anti-policing perspectives grew from mistrust between hooligans and football policing, regularly manifesting aggressive actions, especially upon emotional arousal from losses. Consequently, hooliganism and subsequent violence exemplify multidimensional intricacies, directed by various characteristics.

Table and Figures

Figure 1: Football hooligans (Court, 2019)

Figure 2: Illustration of the interconnected themes extracted from the literature review

Figure 3: Demographic outline

Figure 4: illustration of the interconnected themes extracted from the hooligan interview

Table of Contents

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	5
1.1: RESEARCH QUESTION	8
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW	9
2.1: INTRODUCTION	9
2.2: A SENSE OF BELONGING.....	9
2.3: THE MASCULINE IDENTITY	11
2.4: ALCOHOL CONSUMPTION	14
2.5: RIVALRIES.....	16
2.6: CONCLUSION	18
CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY.....	20
3.1: INTRODUCTION	20
3.2: RESEARCH DESIGN.....	20
3.3: DATA COLLECTION METHOD	21
3.4: SAMPLE.....	23
3.5: ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS.....	24
3.6: DATA ANALYSIS	25
3.8: CONCLUSIONS.....	25
CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION – THE HOOLIGAN IDENTITY.....	27
4.1: INTRODUCTION	27
4.2 FRIENDSHIP, BELONGING AND COMMUNITY	27
4.3: THE WORKING-CLASS AND FOOTBALL CULTURE.....	29
4.4: TEAM PRIDE AND “US VS THEM”	32
4.5: EXCITEMENT.....	34
4.6: HOOLIGAN SHIFT.....	35
4.7: CONCLUSION	36
CHAPTER 5: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION – MEDIA REPRESENTATION AND POLICING SENTIMENTS	39
5.1: INTRODUCTION	39
5.3: MARGINALISATION	40
5.4: POLICING SENTIMENTS	41
5.5: POLICING RECOMMENDATIONS.....	42
5.6: CONCLUSION	44
5.7: STUDY LIMITATION	45
CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION.....	47
BIBLIOGRAPHY.....	52

Chapter 1: Introduction

Scholars define hooliganism as a manifestation of group behaviour within sporting events, exhibiting violent and non-violent tendencies (Nikolic, 2016). Historic narratives of 'us vs them' underscore the hooligan character, serving to facilitate a belonging and rivalry framework (Spaaij, 2008). The principal identifier of a hooligan's character concerns their steadfast allegiance towards their team and community identity (Yusoff, 2015). An Italian study uncovered that 75% of self-identified hooligans were below 30 years of age, meanwhile 85% were male (Meij et al., 2015). Concerningly, young adults exhibit greater tendencies to express aggression, especially when driven by desires to defend their football team's identity. For example, statistical data demonstrates that 70% of football banning orders in England were men between 18-34 years old, accredited to their involvement in football violence (GOV, 2022). The driving influence for football violence is diverse, compounding alcohol consumption, rivalries, masculinity, and a sense of belonging. The average football match attendance in England has increased by 9,330 spectators between 1990/2000 and 2022/2023 (Smith, 2023); therefore, comprehending hooliganism is vital.

This dissertation positions 2 vital concerns within the structure of football hooliganism: firstly, the surge in deviant behaviour, and secondly, the sensationalism of the hooligan identity. Firstly, contemporary football demonstrates a rise in hooligan violence, aggression, and arrest rates. For example, as of July 2022, 1308, banning orders were enforced, 39% of which were new (GOV, 2022). Similarly, pitch invasions by the 2021/2022 season have increased by 127% compared to previous seasons (Sky Sports, 2022). The contemporary data juxtaposes historical statistics, identifying a reduction in football arrests from 13.0 to 4.9 per 100,000 individuals between 2000/2001 to 2014/2015 (Martinez, 2016). Scholars regard the surges in football arrests towards the targeting of hooligan individuals, an approach illuminated by the Euro 2000. To explain, while 965 English fans

were arrested, only 1 was convicted of criminal behaviour (Stott et al., 2008). Nevertheless, the rise of hooligan deviances poses a significant concern that requires examination.

Secondly, the misrepresentation of the hooligan identity intensifies a social hysteria concerning their presence. Scholars have attributed media misinformation towards inciting negative sentiments concerning football hooligans (Martinez, 2026). Namely, articles reinforce hostile sentiments through titles such as, “The drunken, violent, mindless creeps ruin it for everyone” (Poulton, 2005, p.13). Sensationalist discourse contribute towards the alienation of hooligans as folk devils, leading to their trademark as a societal threat (Piskurek, 2018). The dominant narrative of “Aggressive, violence, shaven headed, beer bellied, tattooed, drunk young males”, undeniably serves to perceive hooligans as a moral threat (Poulton, 2005, p.5). Figure 1 illustrates an observable narrative emphasised by the media, displaying the personality mentioned by Poulton (2005, p.5). These impactful narratives facilitate the segregation between football hooligans and society, underscoring narratives of ‘good vs evil’. Consequently, sensationalist reporting has contributed to incidents where football fans carry weapons to prevent potential victimisation (Piskurek, 2018). Henceforth, the false narratives surrounding hooliganism facilitates fear and alienation; thereby, requiring steadfast attention.

Figure 1: Football hooligans (Court, 2019)

Moreover, this dissertation concerns Ostrowsky (2014) comments, suggesting that hooligan violence requires greater understanding (Strang et al., 2018). To explain, the hooligan identity far exceeds the contemporary media narratives of “Savages and animals” (Piskurek, 2018, p.2). Consequently, this flawed perspective contributes towards inappropriate policing tactics, whereby hooligans are over targeted (Martinez, 2016). When interviewed concerning football policing, a Chesterfield fan quotes “How can the police take credit for something they have little involvement with” (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016, p.20). These contrasting sentiments parallel hooligan violence increasing by 51% between 2018/2019 and 2021/2022 (GOV, 2022). In this respect, this dissertation maintains that minimal comprehension of the hooligan phenomenon heightens circumstances of football violence. Therefore, this dissertation exercises a comprehension of the hooligan identity, meanwhile, providing a rational for English football violence and perceptions of football policing.

On that note, chapter 1 explores the framework of the hooligan identity and subsequent football violence. Secondly, chapter 2 exposes the dissertation's qualitative methodology, employing a semi-structured interview alongside an explorative design, interpretivist epistemology and a constructivist ontology. Thirdly, chapter 3 conveys the findings applicable to the hooligan identity and football violence. Fourthly, chapter 4 extracts the hooligan sentiments concerning media representation and football policing. Lastly, chapter 5 concludes this dissertation by answering the examined research questions listed below:

1.1: Research Question

1. *What are the most important factors that contribute towards a hooligans identity?*
2. *To what extent does group interaction and friendship contribute towards hooligan violence?*
3. *What type of violence and aggression and hooligans involved with?*
4. *To what extent, positively or negatively do hooligans perceive football policing and what alternatives would they prefer?*

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1: Introduction

Argued by Dunning (2000), hooliganism has increased drastically within a global setting (Scott et al., 2008). Hooliganism is imbued by mass media sensationalism, often characterizing the term as the English Disease (Poulton, 2005). Consequently, hooliganism has encompassed a moral panic, while hooligans are depicted as folk devils (Steen, 2015). This chapter addresses Ostrowsky's (2014) concern about the minimal comprehensive understanding of hooliganism and violence at football matches (Strang et al., 2018). Therefore, this chapter supplies a fundamental comprehension of the hooligan identity through various academic outlooks, while integrating discourse from hooligans themselves. In this light, 4 key interconnected themes emerged, a sense of belonging, masculinity, alcohol consumption and football rivalries. These themes not only construct the hooligan identity, but additionally affirms the framework for football violence.

2.2: A Sense of Belonging

Despite the complexity of hooliganism, analysis uncovers the desire for belonging as fundamental towards a hooligan's psychosocial outlook (Gumusgul and Acet, 2016). Farrington (1994) articulates that a hooligan's desire for belonging stems from an inadequate upbringing (Piquero et al., 2014). Piotrowski (2006) advances Farrington's argument by discovering young delinquent football fans as characterised by minimal social support (Strang et al., 2014). Consequently, neglected childhood experiences advance the longing for collective belonging, which can be sought through hooliganism. The author of *Psychology Football* similarly positions that those with broken childhood experiences often use hooligan firms as a locus for belonging and aggression (Deriemaeker, 2016). Therefore, belonging within hooligan firms contribute to aggressive attitudes in protecting this new 'family'. Notably, Guilianotti (1994) compounds the term family by likening one's football team to family,

friendship, and community. Hence, a Sparta fan illustrates the credence of friendship as “For many of us friendship, belonging and adventure are just as important as fighting” (Piquero et al., 2014, p.17). On that note, the framework of belonging is a significant motivator that constructs and strengthens a hooligan’s identity.

According to Social Identification Theory, the shared unity amongst football fans often influences their participation in hooligan firms (Lindstrom, 2021). Scholarly reports disclose that hooliganism develops from the inevitability for positive self-esteem within groups of shared beliefs (Knapton et al., 2018). To explain, Eker (2010) suggests a football identity is shaped by mutual appreciation of a football team (Gumusgul and Acet, 2016). For example, the animalistic culture of football moulds behaviour through acts of cheering and hugging (Newson, 2017). Therefore, actions of cheering and hugging facilitates unity amongst strangers, framing tightknit bonds bounded by football.

Contrastingly, actions viewed as positive within football are otherwise seen as nonsensical in boarder society. To explain, despite the prevalence of stranger appreciation within football, it would seem strange in ordinary contexts (Martinez, 2016). Consequently, this duality of perspectives compounds the ‘us vs them’ narrative that drives the hooliganism misrepresentation. As per the literature, the shared appreciation of football heightens the likelihood of joining hooligan firms.

Moreover, hooligan firms fuse social and individual identity through social interactions. Swan et al (2012) affirms through a thematic analysis, that ridged groups propel individual vulnerability (Newson, 2017). On that note, sport viewership heightens emotions amongst deeply passionate football hooligans (Branscome and Wann, 1992). Accordingly, heightened emotional conditions cultivated during game viewership may supply as fuel to aggressive hooligan tendencies. To explain, club success facilitates a varied vulnerability scale within a hooligan’s self-identity; therefore, successes lower anxiousness and vulnerability. For example, Meij et al (2015) notes that success increases the likelihood of positive hooligan firms, self, and group identity. Porat (2010) similarly

finds that team success provided hooligans with joy and a positive outlook on life. By contrast, when games are lost fans are “Troubled by tension” and particularly “Frustrated all week” (Porat, 2010, p.8). Consequently, evidence suggest that game outcomes contribute towards a hooligan’s self-identity. Therefore, a hooligans aggressiveness varies depending on the success of their team, meanwhile, varying their perceived threat to society.

Undoubtably, hooliganism is a symbol of friendship which exists between the “Lads” (Newson, 2017, p.11). A West Ham fan evokes this perspective, suggesting that the “West Ham lads were my family, more than my home family” (Spaaij, 2008, p.17). Notably, ‘family’ expresses the importance of their in-group within their life, essentially, their passion becomes their life. Bill Shankly resonates the desire of family through a “build-up of family” who can say “We’re Liverpool” (Finn, 1994, p.97). Accordingly, the notion of family shows a hooligan’s distorted identity, where football becomes the framework of socialisation. A Middlesbrough fan enhances my remarks, suggesting that “Social status is irrelevant to hooliganism, if you are into it, you are welcome” (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016, p.11). The Middlesbrough fan echoes the background of many hooligans, who come from broken childhoods and use hooligan firms as an alternative family to escape contemporary society. Thereupon, hooliganism participation is through the desire of community, friendship, family, and a new psychosocial outlook.

2.3: The Masculine Identity

No description apart from masculinity satisfactorily encases the nature of football and the hooligan identity. George Orwell describes football as a serious sport with no concept of fair play, paralleling the sport as a sadistic pleasure (Glass, 2014). Sadistic pleasure according to Dunning (2004) represents young males who praise hooliganism as portraying masculinity and excitement (Piquero et al., 2014). To note, 70% of football banning orders in England were given to men between 18 and

34 years old (GOV, 2022). Consequently, studies argue that men in their early 20s use aggression to prove their masculinity against other men (Meij et al., 2015). Masculinity in football overarches drinking, aggression, strength, being feared and a lifelong passion to a particular football team (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016). For example, Feyenoord and Ajax rivals were heavily armed during a 1997 derby, aiming to strengthen their masculinity and their identity (Spaaij, 2008). The hooligan desire to strengthen their masculinity further creates the perception of a folk devil (Steen, 2015). Likewise, the glorification of violence highlights that these influences are quintessential for the transition to manhood (Spaaij, 2008). Accordingly, the emphasis of masculinity within a hooligan identity sustains the folk devil narrative of “shaven-headed, beer-bellied, tattooed, drunk and disorderly young males” (Poulton, 2005, p.5). Thus, paralleling the literature, masculinity is embedded within a hooligan identity, providing strength, purpose, and meaning.

Furthermore, the desire for masculine validation serves to distract from the boredom of society, thereby providing hooligans with a sense of direction. To explain, a Newcastle United fan conveys that masculine violence distracts them from their “Boredom” of ordinary life (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016, p.10). Similarly, a Feyenoord fan notes a “Overwhelming” feeling from masculine aggression, likened to a “Sense of power and a sense of control” (Spaaij, 2008, p.7). Scholarly examination reveals that those who pursue excitement in hooligan activities express greater levels of masculine aggression. For example, Spaaij (2008) reports that hooliganism arises from the absence of acceptable masculine role models; therefore, focusing on excitement, adventure, and masculine validation over the ordinary life (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016). Case in point, the armed Feyenoord firms demonstrate a comprehensible picture of the interrelationship between masculinity, excitement, aggression, and perceptions of fear (Spaaij, 2008). Ayres and Treadwell (2012) further illustrate the interrelationship between masculinity and excitement, asserting this relationship encompasses “Breaking free from the restraints of the working week and losing control” (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016, p.93). The term ‘breaking free’ parallels interviewees awareness of masculinity

rivalry as “An amazing adrenaline rush” (Radmann, 2013, p.7). As per the literature, the prevalence of masculinity facilitates a purpose within a hooligan’s life.

Similarly, since the late 1800s, masculinity has encapsulated the traditional culture of football. For example, West Ham hooligans take pride in their traditional masculine values, influencing their desire to maintain a rough image (Spaij, 2008). Notably, the traditional masculine identity derives from the historical working-class man, where aggression parallels manliness. The traditional working-class ideology structures a framework where a culture of quasi-violence is regarded as supportive to a hooligan’s identity (Finn, 1994). Quasi-violence concerns apply to offences against sports and legal regulations namely, aggression, and physical violence (Knapton et al., 2018). Therefore, Dunning (1998) asserts that varying degrees of quasi-violence constructs varying social status classification (Spaij, 2008). For example, the Manchester United Red Army during the 1974-1975 season destroyed football grounds across England due to their relegation from the top league in English Football. Consequently, the Red Army’s high masculine aggression and socialisation influenced the introduction of crowd segregation and fencing at football pitches in England (The Firms, 2014). Their embodiment of the traditional masculine identity ensured the Red Army was the face of the hooligan moral panic (Steen, 2015). As such, Ian Taylor likens the Red Army’s success to the embodiment of masculinity within the socialisation of quasi-violence (Piskurek, 2018). The socialisation itself contributes towards the awareness of traditional masculine values, which changes a football fan from ordinary to a hooligan. As per the literature, masculinity defines a hooligan’s historical culture, while providing an environment for socialisation that grows the hooligan and folk devil narrative.

Additionally, masculinity solidifies a football fans collective belonging and solidarity within a hooligan firm. Masculinity affirms hooligan solidarity through the application of aggressive banners, chants, and uniforms (Doidge and Lieser, 2017). Dunning and Colleagues (1988) further argue that

masculinity provides commonality amongst all hooligans, therefore, fostering deep connections (Spaij, 2008). Maffesoli (1996) presents this social connection as blocking the influence of society, where intelligence is favoured over masculinity (Newson, 2017). The juxtaposition of hooligans and society compounds articles which propels folk devil narratives, namely, “Thanks to the actions of a band of thugs who call themselves football fans” (Poulton, 2005, p.10). Consequently, the sensationalist attack on hooligans furthers masculine solidarity to heighten their masculine image. For instance, regarded by Guilianotti (1999) social capital is fundamental to a hooligan’s identity. This is presented through published and organised fights between rival hooligan firms (Gumusgul and Acet, 2016). Despite published violence, a West Ham hooligan conveys that in public they have never been harmed by a hooligan. For instance, the fan states “They knew I was working there” but “There was no point in mixing up these things,” as “My work has nothing to do with football” (Spaij, 2008, p.16). While hooliganism desires attention, masculinity and violence, there are evident moral codes to keep their violence within their in-group. As per the literature, masculinity increases in-group solidarity while contributing a folk devil narrative through the publication of their violence, however, hooligans attest to keeping their conflict within hooligan grounds.

2.4: Alcohol Consumption

Alcohol consumption has long been affiliated alongside hooliganism. Millward’s (2009) research discovered that alcohol consumption changes psychological behaviour, notably, boosting aggressive tendencies (Strang et al., 2018). Carinbella et al (1996) parallels Millward’s observations, detecting aggressive tendencies by Aston Villa fans upon alcohol consumption (Deriemaeker, 2016). Similarly, pitch invasions during the 1980 Scottish Cup Final were linked to alcohol consumption, which introduced football alcohol legislation in Scotland (Finn, 1994). These reports complement broader statistics, suggesting that 50% of alcoholic men are aggressive (Beck and Heinz, 2013). Consequently, Scholars positions that Alcohol Myopia contributes towards hooligan violence. Importantly, Alcohol

Myopia diminishes individual processing capacity, rational and attention span (Sevincer and Oettingen, 2014). A Leeds United fan demonstrates Alcohol Myopia, suggesting that “Alcohol gives me a sense that I am unbeatable in confrontation” (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016, p.14). Thereupon, Alcohol Myopia can hinder rational, which increases irrational judgement favouring aggression and violence. As per the literature, alcohol to a varying degree contributes towards aggressiveness within hooligans.

Furthermore, policing sentiments underscore the interrelationship between alcohol consumption, hooliganism, and violence. For example, the UK police position evidence correlating alcoholism to disorderly behaviour in football and society (Sky Sports, 2022). Notably, British Crime Victim Surveys illustrate victims of violence perceive their attacker as influenced by alcohol (Beynon et al., 2017). To illustrate, alcohol consumption contributed towards 40% of violent crime in England (Office for Health and Improvement and Disparities, N.D). Henceforth, the heightened emotional arousals within football fans may increase the prominence of alcohol aggression. Schaap et al (2015) through observations of football matches in the Netherlands, discovered the community atmosphere encouraged binge drinking aggression, while alcohol prohibited stadiums reduced the likelihood of violence (Strang et al., 2018). Consequently, The Sporting Event Act 1985 barred alcohol consumption in view of the pitch and drunkenness within a sporting event (CPS, 2023). Later statistics from the 2011/12 to 2012/13 season saw a drop concerning alcohol crime from 800 offences to 549 (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016). Thereupon, evidence suggests a relationship between alcohol and aggressive hooligans to a varying degree.

Importantly, Shephard (1991) argues that group drinking, and aggressiveness are embedded within football culture. Guilianotti (1995) parallels this by noting the tradition of alcohol consumption in sports (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016). For example, 23% of English men consume alcohol, while the 2010 World Cup increased Budweiser sales by 19% (Alcohol Concern, n.d.). While alcohol is pivotal

to a hooligan's identity, the foundation of hooliganism creates violence rather than the influence of alcohol. For example, Martinez (2016) argues that alcohol plays a minimal role in creating and sustaining hooliganism. Likewise, behavioural studies note that alcohol merely aggravates existing aggressive tendencies through Alcohol Myopia (Fritz et al., 2013). Therefore, hooligan solidarity alongside bonding encourages traditional group drinking which leads to Alcohol Myopia and in-direct aggression. According to Martinez (2016), fans seek out establishments that sell alcohol pre-game. Martinez's (2016) suggestion may provide ground to the increase in alcohol offences between 2019/20-2021/22. For instance, Covid-19 lockdown deprived social gatherings which is central to a hooligan identity; therefore, post lockdown exemplified the desire for group drinking, while increasing the risk of Alcohol Myopia by increased attendance. Notably, those who visit a pub 2-3 times a week increased from 3% in 2019 to 4% in 2023 (Statista, 2023). Accordingly, hooligan solidarity post-covid cultivated an environment propelling a greater desire for group drinking. As regarded by the literature, group drinking is embedded within hooliganism, facilitating group solidarity with in-direct outcomes of aggression that sustain a folk devil narrative.

2.5: Rivalries

Football rivalries materialise as a repercussion of the former themes; however, football rivalries are quintessential to a hooligan's identity. Importantly, Armstrong (1998) mirrors the hooligan identity alongside a 'us vs them' ideology (Spaaij, 2008). Stead and Rookwood (2007) observed that the 'us vs them' narrative heightens group solidarity alongside rival aggressiveness (Strang et al., 2018). Rivals are challenged through various foul chants and intimidation, thereby, sustaining a folk devil narrative. The foul chants often portray hooligans as a group of pathetic skinheads who are the folk devil to society (Piskurek, 2018). For instance, rival taunts against David Beckham reinforces an overarching folk devil narrative with chants such as, "your wife is a w***re and we hope your kid d*es of cancer" (Poulton, 2005, p.9). On the other side, Knapton et al (2018) correlates rival

aggressiveness towards one's inclusion within their football culture. For example, Diekhof et al (2014) discovered that hooligans rejected unfair offers from rivals at rates significantly higher than their in-group hooligans (Strang et al., 2018). Accordingly, Diekhof et al (2014) findings encourage the debate of hooligans favouring loyalty and sustaining rivalries. As argued by the literature, rivalries are fundamental to a hooligan's identity, establishing solidarity which forms an environment where a folk devil narrative grows.

Additionally, the tendency to defend a home ground serves to facilitate hooliganism and football rivalries. To explain, the phenomenon of defending what hooligans perceive as crucial enlarges their emotional identity (Wann et al., 1999). Accordingly, hooligans perceive defending their home territory as a necessary duty (Strang et al., 2018). For instance, interviews by Porat (2010, p.9) determine that the club stadium is a "Home", and hooligans have a strong willingness to "Defend their joy". Henceforth, hooligans are prideful in their obligations to their team, territory, and developing rivalries. Similarly, West Ham interviewees compound their duty as a football fan stating, "We wanted to defend our territory in the East End of London" (Spaaij, 2008, p.15). The West Ham sentiment illustrates that hooligans form within areas of deep-rooted culture, encompassing loyalty and masculinity. Hence, Piotrowski (2006) observed that hooligans are bounded to protect the club's image and identity from any rival aggression (Strang et al., 2018). Consequently, hooligan dedication often influences aggressive behaviour when losses occur during games (Meij et al., 2015). For example, Manchester United fans fought Manchester City fans after their 2-1 loss at the FA Cup Final (Andrews, 2023). To note, aggression upon a loss is aggravated by the proximity of home and away (Strang et al., 2018). Thereupon, defending hooligan identity, alongside the proximity of rival fans increases the likelihood of aggressiveness and propelling a moral panic narrative. According to the literature, the hooligan's identity is intertwined with their home stadium and the propensity of aggressive tendencies varies upon the success of the team and the proximity of rival hooligans.

Moreover, hooligans utilise football rivalries as a means of excitement and masculine presentation. Ostrowsky (2014) addresses that hooligans experience increased adrenaline when confronting opposition. Ostrowsky (2014) observations suggest that rival confrontation elevates emotional arousals, while heightening solidarity and group deviance (Strang et al., 2018). Accordingly, the joy of rival confrontation produces never ending cycle of solidarity and aggression. Likewise, an interviewed hooligan describes rival confrontation as a “Amazing adrenaline rush” and “Nothing compares to it” (Radmann, 2013, p.7). The adrenaline experienced by confrontation distracts hooligans from the constraints in contemporary society; thereupon, hooliganism and rivalries are a product of emotions, identity, and experiences. Understandably, most hooligans are brought up from inadequate upbringings (Piquero et al., 2014). A study by Pomares and Villanueva with 490 young adults between 18-20 years old discovered significant links between childhood and deviance. Their study concluded that unfavourable childhood experiences significantly contribute towards future deviant behaviour (Pomares and Villanueva, 2020). Thereupon, hooligan rivalries may be the desire for excitement from a neglected childhood rather than a natural desire for violence. As portrayed by the literature, a hooligan’s desire for excitement propels rivalries, while contributing to a societal moral panic.

2.6: Conclusion

In conclusion, hooliganism is a complex multifaceted phenomenon encapsulated by misinformation and sensationalism (Poulton, 2005). Nonetheless, this chapter has asserted that hooliganism incorporates a frame of collective bonding, masculinity, alcohol consumption and football rivalries. Figure 2 visualises the interconnectivity of the themes observed in the literature review. Firstly, hooligans often originate from fractured backgrounds, which offers justification for their participation in hooligan firms of like-minded individuals (Deriemaeker, 2016). A hooligan firm functions as one’s safety, comfort, belonging and family to those without one. This is suggested by a

West Ham fan stating, “The West Ham lads were my family, more than my home family” (Spaij, 2008, p.17). Secondly, masculinity enhances the sense of belonging, loyalty, and group drinking (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016). Thirdly, alcohol consumption in football undertones a hooligan’s desire for group solidarity and maintaining a masculine image. For example, Shepard (1991) notes that group drinking, and aggressiveness is within football culture. Group drinking contributes towards masculine violence through a Leeds United fan stating, “Alcohol gives me a sense that I am unbeatable in confrontation” (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016, p.14). Lastly, the ‘us vs them’ narrative within the belonging of a hooligan firm contributes towards rival aggressiveness (Strang et al., 2018). Likewise, interviewed hooligans describe the atmosphere of male rival confrontation as an “Amazing adrenaline rush” (Radmann, 2013, p.7). Thereby, the masculinity identity of confrontation provides hooligans with adrenaline and excitement. Accordingly, the factors that influence hooliganism are all inter-connected, fostering hooligan violence and contributing towards a folk devil narrative.

Figure 2: Illustration of the interconnected themes extracted from the literature review

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1: Introduction

This chapter explores the dissertations research design, focusing on a qualitative structure that harmonises the voice and experiences of football hooligans. The research methodology is structured upon the 36 sources utilised within the literature review. Additionally, this chapter addresses the implementation of the semi-structured interview and participation recruitment. Lastly, ethical considerations are addressed alongside the thematic framework.

3.2: Research Design

The literature review guided the research investigation, whereby Ostrowsky's (2014) argued the minimal understanding of hooliganism and hooligan violence (Strang et al., 2018). The literature review discovered that hooliganism is multifaceted, influenced by collective belonging, masculinity, alcohol consumption and football rivalries. Henceforth, this dissertation aims to uncover:

- 1. What are the most important factors that contribute towards a hooligans identity?*
- 2. To what extent does group interaction and friendship contribute towards hooligan violence?*
- 3. What type of violence and aggression and hooligans involved with?*
- 4. To what extent, positively or negatively do hooligans perceive football policing and what alternatives would they prefer?*

To contextualise the subjectivity of the hooligan identity, a qualitative research design seems desirable. Qualitative research focuses on the "Nature of phenomena" alongside their qualities, perspective, context, and the underlying meaning concerning social phenomena (Ugwu and Eze,

2023, p.1). Considering the focus of this dissertation concerns the nature of hooliganism, a qualitative approach argued by (Ugwu and Eze, 2023, p.1) appears appropriate. Likewise, hooligan's studies have utilised a qualitative approach, namely, Yusoff (2015), and Radmann (2013). The casualness of qualitative interview facilitates a natural extraction of feelings and experiences (Ruslin et al., 2022). Henceforth, extracting 'feeling and experiences' provides rich data, which is quintessential to comprehend a multifaceted phenomenon like hooliganism

Additionally, this dissertation adopts an interpretivist epistemology and a constructionist ontology. Interpretivism positions reality is subjective and culturally constructed, whereby comprehending social reality is through the individuals experience of that reality (Jamshed, 2014). According to Radmann (2013), the hooligan complexity requires an outlook of subjectivity when interviewing participants. Radmann (2013) illudes that despite negative labels, various hooligans have subjective reasons for joining, which researchers should take into consideration. Likewise, constructionism finds that culture is within a continuous state of construction and reconstruction (Bryman, 2016). Spaaij (2008) recognises the reconstruction of hooliganism by suggesting that "football hooliganism has gradually evolved into a persistent transnational subculture" (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016, p.10).

3.3: Data Collection Method

Semi-structured interviews were best suited for this research, whereby complimenting the studies epistemological and ontological positions. Semi-structured interviews are exploratory in nature, utilising general guides to facilitate the exploration of subjective narratives and complex issues (Ruslin et al., 2022). These interviews encourage the natural expenditure of individual thought, expression and feeling, whereby easing topics of sensitive or complex issues (Adams, 2015).

Similarly, the utilisation of open and close-ended questions facilitates individual thought expression which allows for greater critical responses (Bryman, 2016). Henceforth, the mixture of open-ended and closed-ended questions ensure the facilitation of potential critical thinking.

The research guide was influenced by the 4 interconnected themes discovered from the literature review (See Figure 2). Hence, the interview guide encompassed 4 topics with 3 to 5 questions within them (See Appendix G). The topics covered are 'Belonging', 'Alcohol', 'Masculinity' and 'Football rivalries'. Prompts and probes were similarly utilised to aid in extracting rich information from participants. For example, prompts such as, "Why do you think football fans hold greater bonds than those in society?" and "Does bonding increase the sensitivity to rival aggression?". The interview concerns revealing the multifaceted reality of hooliganism; therefore, open-ended questioning facilitates the participants thought expansion. Initial questions surrounded the participants football background, which was gathered using a 'Participant Background Questionnaire' (See Appendix F). These background questions ease the concern of Fontana and Frey (2000), suggesting that the initial period of interviewing is crucial for bonding (Jacob and Furgerson, 2012).

The research contained 6 interviews as Morgan Et al (2002) found that thematic saturation occurs between interviews 5-6 (Guest, Namey and Chen, 2020). To explain, thematic saturation arises once no new themes are extracted from the interviews (Guest. Namey and Chen, 2020). Interviews were conducted in January, aligning with the middle of the English football season. Interviews took place within cafes nearby Old Trafford (Manchester United), St Andrew's (Birmingham City), London Stadium (West Ham), The Den (Millwall) and the King Power Stadium (Leicester city). Preceding interviews, participants signed a 'Consent Form' and a 'Participant Background Questionnaire', obtaining information of their age, football team and hooligan firm affiliation (see Appendix E and

Appendix F). On average, interviews lasted 40 minutes with interviewees neglecting to ask further questions. Within 24 of interviewing, transcripts were forged, and audio recordings were destroyed.

3.4: Sample

This dissertation applied a purposeful sampling technique, whereby participations were recruitment owing to their robust awareness in the research topic (Palinkas et al., 2013). Though purposeful sampling allows for information-rich participations, the generalisability of results is limited (Coyne, 1997). However, this dissertation concerns hooliganism within England, therefore minimising worries of non-generalisability, nonetheless they still remain. Additionally, this dissertation adopted the sampling handbook authored by Rubin and Rubin (1995) to facilitate participant recruitment. Therefore, participants should be knowledgeable and keen on discourse (Robinson, 2014). On that note, this dissertation adopted a homogenous sample of 21–37-year-old males that fit within 2 criteria. Firstly, participants should follow either Manchester United, Millwall, Leicester City, Birmingham City and West Ham. Statistics discloses that these teams represent the greatest percentage of banning orders during 2022-2023 (GOV, 2023), denoting that participants could produce a fortune of information. Secondly, participant should self-identify or possess affiliation with hooligan firms. The participants age distribution parallels findings from an Italian football study, unpacking that 97% of hooligans were under 30 years old (Meij et al., 2015). On that note, figure 3 illustrates the breakdown of the studies sample.

Figure 3: Demographic outline

Gender	Pseudonym	Age	Football Team	Hooligan Firm
Male	A1	27	Manchester United	Red Army
Male	A2	21	Millwall	Bushwackers
Male	A3	24	Leicester City	Baby Squad
Male	A4	23	Birmingham City	ZULU Warriors
Male	A5	25	West Ham	Inner City Firm
Male	A6	36	Manchester United	Red Army

Participant recruitment involved delivering introductory messages to football away social media accounts (See Appendix B). However, from 37 introductory messages delivered, only 6 accounts responded back. The minimal response rate parallels the negative sentiments that hooligans retain of external media interference (Martinez, 2016). Despite this, once contacted, emails were shared, and participants received a 'Participant Information Sheet' and a 'Contact Information Sheet' (See Appendix C and Appendix D). From initial contact, interviews were conducted within 3-4 weeks.

3.5: Ethical Considerations

The misrepresentation of hooliganism fuels an unwillingness for discourse, as suspicion overpowers a hooligans mindset (Strang et al., 2018). Henceforth, the BSA 'State of Ethical Practice' is utilised to consult ethical considerations. Importantly, research began only once ethical approval and consent was obtained (See Appendix A and Appendix E). Participating interviewees received a 'Participant Information Sheet', providing details about the research and ensuring participant confidentiality (See Appendix C). Participants were informed concerning their withdrawal rights, doing so ensured the destruction of their data within 24 hours of said request. This parallels the BSA's ethical protocol, emphasising participant awareness concerning all aspect of the research process (BSA, 2017). All

gathered data bounded to GDPR regulations, meanwhile, participants were informed about the processing of their data. Interview audio recordings and transcripts were stored in a password locked google drive account, with access restricted to the researcher only. Simultaneously, physical consent forms were stored in a locked file cabinet at the researchers address. Pseudonyms were utilised to safeguard anonymity, which minimises hooligan's suspicion over discourse. Post final submission, participants have the prospect to examine the findings, and all related data would be deleted.

3.6: Data Analysis

This study employed a thematic analysis framework, which involves identifying, organising, and extracting themes from a dataset (Lorelli et al., 2017). The thematic framework "Systematically organise and analyse complex data sets" by sorting key-themes and sub-themes (Dawadi, 2020, p.62). An inductive and deductive approach was adopted, which combines categories from the literature review with the interview data (Lorelli et al., 2017). Dawadi (2020, p.63) proports that this approach "Maximises the overall depth of the analysis", concluding in rigorous findings. The coding categories are founded through a "Re-reading" within a "Systematic way" (Dawadi, 2020, p.63). Henceforth, the thematic analysis framework provides the production of rigorous results.

3.8: Conclusions

This chapter has justified the research elements utilised in this dissertation. The qualitative research design delivered a robust portrait of the hooligans subjective identity, Semi-structured interviews advanced the extraction of the hooligan identity, encompassed questions based on academic literature. Purposeful sampling benefited the recruitment of football hooligans incorporated in this

study. The ethical framework was assessed to diminish participant harm and heighten safety. Finally, the thematic analysis framework was recognized and assessed.

Chapter 4: Findings and Discussion – The Hooligan Identity

4.1: Introduction

This chapter illuminates the extensive narrative of hooliganism from the perspectives of interviewees. The themes are listed in a descending order, acknowledging a ranking in prevalence, whereby, the arrangement advances from most applicable to least applicable. This approach guarantees a digestible comprehension of which themes contribute more notably to a hooligans identity.

4:2 Friendship, Belonging and Community

The desire for belonging was likened as the greatest motivator for interviewees to join hooligan firms. This complements Knapton et al (2018) study, finding that friendship compounded reasons for hooliganism. Interviewees unequivocally portrayed the benefits of firms in establishing robust friendships.

“I felt like making friends, getting to know more people and just being around people with the same passion as me”. (A2)

Interviewees similarly noted the utilisation of masculinity in forming social bonds within firms. Research acknowledges that collective aggression elevates social fusion within in-groups (Lindström, 2021). On that note, friendships are interwoven alongside aggression and aggression facilitates friendship (Meij et al., 2015). Interviewee (A6), exposed this perception, acknowledging the importance of aggression for sustaining friendships.

“When there used to be organised fights, it was groups fighting groups, it was a great getting into a scrap with your mates”. (A6)

Similarly, the masculine approach to pre-game drinking functioned to solidify friendships. Pre-existing literature persists that alcohol consumption encourages friendships and group connections within football environments (Wakefield and Wann, 2006). On that note, the interviewees reinforced the importance of pre-drinking towards the facilitation of friendship.

“I’ve met loads of good lads while drinking with them near Old Trafford, I made lifelong friends”. (A1)

Interviewees further regarded football rivalries as a source of collective unification. Glass (2014) regards the collective hatred towards a rival football team as a source for social identification within firms. Hence, rival games heighten emotional arousals between hooligans, thereby heightening social collectiveness (Branscombe and Wann, 1992). Accordingly, Interviewees disclosed a unified comradery when facing rivals.

“All West Ham fans can agree that we hate Millwall, we even have a chant saying that we hate Millwall”. (A5)

“All the lads in the firm hate Liverpool, we hate scousers”. (A1)

These collective unifications are reinforced through cramped celebrations, hugging, and cheering within football matches (Newson, 2017). Interviewees unanimously drew comparisons between football celebrations and one’s introduction towards deep-rooted friendships. More precisely, literature contest that football fans within cramped conditions foster greater social bonds (Piquero

et al., 2014). Henceforth, interviewees equated goal celebrations towards the facilitation of friendship.

“I can go to games and if we score, hug a stranger next to me like he’s my best friend and I’ve known him all my life”. (A1)

Convincingly, these relationships contribute towards a belief of brotherhood between hooligans. Pre-existing literature pinpoints that these firms represent an individual’s imaginary community, whereby providing a social safety net (Guilianotti, 1994). In essence, these friendships provide the foundation of joy (Porat, 2010). Quite rightly, interviewees noted the significance of their constructed community within their lives.

“Were a little community, West Ham a special team, and we all consider ourselves family”. (A5)

“I wanted a group where I can feel at home with, that’s why I love this”. (A4)

4.3: The Working-Class and Football Culture

Moreover, the interviewees affirmed their working-class framework as advancing their advocacy for hooligan firms. To explain, the working-class culture encourages an environment of violence, whereby aggression is utilised for self-protection (Guilianotti, 1994). Thereupon, the working-class source of hooliganism favours a culture of aggressive masculinity (Piquero et al., 2014). However, interviewees never candidly expressed enduring inadequate upbringings, which challenges scholarly literature (Piquero et al., 2014). Most interviewees drew correlations between their working-class heritage and their association within hooligan violence.

"I got into a lot of fights, for people like us it's just a part of life to fight your way to the top".

(A6)

"We have to be strong we have no choice, if we were weak then people will walk all over us".

(A1)

The interviewees responses parallels Spaaij's (2008) conclusions, indicating that West Ham hooligans likened their identity towards their working-class customs. Interviewee A6 specifics that fighting is a "Part of life", whereby illustrating the inseparability of violence and hooliganism. Arguably, "Fight your way to the top" (A6) highlights the quintessential transition from boyhood to manhood noted by Spaaij (2008).

Concerningly, Bryant and McElroy (1997) theories that excess alcohol contributes towards hooligan violence (Kleomanis, 2005). More broadly, 50% of alcoholic men studied by Beck and Heinz (2013) portrayed violent tendencies. Despite contemporary literature, interviewees disregarded the association between hooligan violence and alcohol. To be precise, interviewees equated hooligan violence towards the working-class culture rather than alcohol.

"Drinking don't matter mate; we would be fighting whether we are drunk or not, that's just who we are". (A6)

The interviewees denial parallels pre-existing studies concluding that regular alcohol consumers often deny the repercussions of their actions (T, 2020). Likewise, Strang et al (2018) transcribes that prolonged alcohol consumption modifies brain functions such as, behaviour, emotions and rational, which may undernote the interviewees denials. Despite this, hooligan literature compounds the

naturalness of drunkenness and fighting within a football and working-class culture (Shephard, 1991). Interviewee A1 likens Shephard (1991) arguing that “Where I grew up fighting was as normal as eating”. Arguably, these sentiments reiterate the acceptance of violence within the football and working-class culture (Guilianotti, 1994).

Consequently, the acceptance of violence functions as the foundation of social hierarchy, whereby hooligan firms utilise aggression to be viewed as the strongest. Hooligan studies portray the contest of masculine identities through the exhibitions of strength and aggression (Strang et al., 2018). To explain, the intoxicating relationship between armed Feyenoord and Ajax hooligans demonstrates the interwovenness of aggression and firm status (Spaij, 2008). Henceforth, interviewees commonly positioned the importance of social hierarchy and the utilization of aggression to maintain their status.

“You can’t let your rival team come to your home ground and make you look weak, it’s just unacceptable”. (A6)

The interviewees regularly asserted that their masculinity facilitated strength, therefore heightening the perception of their firms. Interviewee A2 communicates that their usage of an aggressive presentation ensures that “Nobody messes with us”. Literature recognises that firms such as, the Manchester United Red Army utilises an aggressive presentation to be feared (Steen, 2015). Accordingly, Interview A1 encompasses this presentation noting that “Old Trafford is a fortress”. Evidently, the masculine working class identity encompassing the hooligan and overarching football culture.

4.4: Team Pride and “Us vs Them”

Interviewees further established that social hierarchies foster team pride and ultimately rivalries.

Aggressiveness is often used by highly identified fans to protect the pride of their team (Wann et al., 1999). Throughout the interviewees the theme of humiliation through losses were apparent.

Academic literature contends that a hooligan’s self-worth is inseparably interwoven with club success, whereby club defeats are judged as individual defeats (Meij et al., 2015). Precisely, interviewees likened success towards collective pride and losses towards collective humiliation.

“Losing to Millwall at home is humiliating”. (A5)

“Yeh, it gives us pride, being the best gives Millwall it’s meaning you know, look at our history”. (A2)

King (2001) connotes that hooligans are bounded by protection, specifically, protecting their team through violence (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016). Interviewee A5 parallels King (2001) conclusions noting that, “Losing to Millwall at home is humiliating, my mates were telling me they couldn’t let Millwall leave without getting punched”. In essence, hooligans perceive violence as a form of loyalty in protecting their team’s pride (Guilianotti, 1999).

Additionally, the interviewees brought forth the connection between game losses and emotional impact. To note, defeat heightens individual aggressiveness by impacting a hooligan’s pride. For example, losses during the World Cup increased domestic violence by 38% in England (CPS, 2022). Subsequently, the interviewees likened defeats with emotion pain and aggression.

“But a loss really does hurt, but losing to your rival is even worse”. (A2)

*“A loss hurts, and it affects everyone, I f*cking hate it no matter who we lose to”. (A1)*

Accordingly, Gumusgul and Acet (2016) theorised those emotions from defeat undertones the inception of hooligan violence. For example, losses impact individual pride, whereby causing emotional deterioration and ultimately aggression towards rival fans (Wann et al., 1999).

Furthermore, interviewees recognised a territorial aspect within their identity and portrayal of aggression. To note, the proximity of home/away fans can influence the level of violence (Strang et al., 2018). Yusoff (2015) concludes that the closeness of rival fans influences the degree of verbal aggression caused. Literature evidently cultivates the presence of a territorial defense within a hooligan psychosocial outlook. Henceforth, interviewees regarded an evident hatred towards rival teams.

“I rather be dead than support Liverpool or City”. (A6)

“I’ve said it many times, if you support Liverpool, city, or Arsenal then you aren’t welcomed into Old Trafford”. (A1)

“West Ham and Millwall, we hate each other”. (A5)

Interviewees embodied an overarching hatred that encompass football rivalries and the hooligan identity. Stead and Rookwood (2007) proclaimed that collective hatred ensures approval for violence against rival teams (Strang et al., 2018). Interviewee A1 evokes these sentiments by Stead and Rookwood (2007), disclosing that they punched a Manchester City fan for “Entering a United pub”. Arguably, the United pub functions as a ‘home’, thereby, attacking the Manchester City fan

resembles one defending their home (Deriemaeker, 2016). Likewise, Interviewee A6 regarded their compliance within this study to the researcher being a 'Manchester United fan'. In essence, territorial perspectives and team pride undertone a hooligan's ideology while influencing violence.

4.5: Excitement

Dunning (2000) reattains that young men utilise hooligan firms as the catalyst for masculinity and excitement (Piquero et al., 2014). Henceforth, interviewees describe the portrayal of masculine aggression provides an outlook of excitement, thrill, and rush.

"Shouting at other teams is fun and to see their reaction is even better, gives me a rush".

(A4)

"When you're in a small confrontation it's exciting, you don't know how it will end". (A5)

The interviewees sentiments reflect those concluded by Cleland and Cashmore (2016); they find that hooliganism combats the dullness of common life. For example, interviewed hooligans paralleled rival confrontation as a "Amazing adrenaline rush", whereby negating the boredom of life (Radmann, 2013, p.7). As a result, Interviewee A1 likens their masculine aggression towards a "Thrill when I can just let loose". Consequently, the Interviewees "Thrill" (A1) from violence parallels George Orwell's description of football as a sadistic pleasure (Glass, 2014). Henceforth, Spaaij (2008) likens these emotions towards those who seek exhilaration and emotional stimulation.

On that note, rival confrontation provides the emotional stimulation of excitement sought by hooligans. Pomares and Villanueva (2020) discovered significant links between childhood upbringing and the propensity of future deviance. To explain, Piquero et al (2014) likens the utilisation of

violence for excitement within the hooligan's working-class upbringing. The Interviewees parallel these conclusions, noting that rival confrontation heightens emotional arousals of joy and excitement.

"It's fun to mess around with rivals, it's amazing to see your team win and for rivals to cry".

(A5)

The interviewees statements align with wider literature concerning the inter-relationship between rivalries and emotional arousal. Research reinforces that rival confrontation accelerates adrenaline and a sense of purpose (Radmann, 2013). Accordingly, interviewee A5 similarly regards these findings through suggesting that "Confrontation with a rival is fun". Such emotional arousals undoubtedly heighten collective solidarity as rival confrontation are often conducted in groups (Meij et al., 2015). Interviewee A6 parallels Meij et al (2015) conclusion of group violence, stating that violence occurred with "Groups fighting groups". Accordingly, rival confrontation provides a sense of excitement that in-directly contributes towards group solidarity.

4.6: Hooligan Shift

Throughout the interviews, respondents noted a shift concerning the structure and output of violence within hooligan firms. To illustrate, contemporary football minimises the prevalence of the traditional working-class through an 81% middle class population (Kleomanis, 2005). Interviewees liken this change in population alongside a shift within the structure and violence of hooligan firms.

"Now people fight over emotion, there is no rules to it, fights happen whenever and wherever you know. It's not structured like before; the old school hooligans are dead". (A1)

“It definitely is not on the level of the violence that we saw before.” (A2)

These statements are reflected by Gumusgul and Acet (2016), concluding that modern hooligan violence is spontaneous rather than organised. Interviewee A5 further persists that “Derby days were a lot more violent”, this suggests a shift concerning the output of violence. However, this perspective negates the 39% increase in banning orders between 2021-2022 (GOV, 2022). A Coventry City fan similarly reiterates that modern football rarely suffers from strategically organised violence (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016). Henceforth, the fluidity of violence has moved away from organised fights towards verbal “threats at rivals, swearing and maybe throwing something at them” (A5). This shift resembles that experienced in the 1960s, whereby violence transcended from attacking players and towards other fans (Deriemaeker, 2016). Accordingly, violence has shifted from organised towards spontaneous violence highlighted by emotional arousal.

4.7: Conclusion

In conclusion, hooliganism is a multifaceted phenomenon, encompassing several determinants. Firstly, interviewees articulated friendships as an influence for affiliating with hooligan firms. Interviewees cited appreciating “Being around people with the same passion as me” (A2). Literature contends that belonging overarches narratives for hooligan firm affiliation (Knapton et al., 2018). The confined nature of football celebrations aids the collective unification of individuals within football groups (Newson, 2017). To explain, interviewees specified the power to “Hug a stranger next to me like he’s my best friend” (A1). These emotional bonds encourage aggression, and in turn aggression fosters social solidarity. Interviewee A6 flags that “It was a great getting into a scrap with your mates”. This supports Meij et al (2015) results that friendships are interconnected alongside aggression, and aggression facilitates friendship. Henceforth, belonging poses a significant contributor towards one’s admiration towards hooliganism.

Secondly, the working-class culture inherent in football serves as the framework for hooligan firms. Namely, the working-class root of hooliganism encourages a culture of aggressive masculinity (Piquero et al., 2014). Concerningly, literature indicates broad correlation between testosterone regulation and aggressiveness propensity in young men (Strang et al., 2018). This is alarming as 75% of hooligans within an Italian study were under 30 years of age, whereby extremely susceptible to violent outburst. Consequently, the acceptance of violence encourages an environment of violent social hierarchy. For example, interviewees pictured not allowing rivals to “Make you look weak” (A6). This proposition parallels the dynamic between armed Feyenoord and Ajax hooligans, demonstrating the relationship between aggression, fear perception and social hierarchy (Spaij, 2008).

Thirdly, a robust team pride greatly influenced the interviewees participation in hooligan firms. Arguably, aggressiveness protects, aids, and solidifies one’s attachment to their football team and hooligan firm (Wann et al., 1999). The interviewees asserted emotional arousals when confronting rivals like, “Losing to Millwall at home is humiliating” (A5). Academic literature expresses the interwovenness between hooliganism and protection through violence (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016). To note, interviewee A5 communicates that their friends “Couldn’t let Millwall leave without getting punched”. Arguably, interviewees portrayed an overarching hatred that encompassed the hooligan identity.

Fourthly, young men adopt firms as the catalyst for excitement and masculinity (Piquero et al., 2014). Interviewees demonstrated that “Shouting at other teams is fun” (A4) and encountering “Small confrontations its exciting” (A5). Interviewees sentiments portrayed the usefulness of firms towards combating the stagnation of contemporary society. Interviewees additionally stipulate that

Derby confrontation “Dominates your mind” (A6) and is a “Thrill when I can just let loose” (A1). On that note, hooliganism and rival confrontation allocates the emotional stimulation sought by hooligans.

Lastly, Interviewees elucidated a notably shift in the structure and manifestation of violence within hooliganism. To illustrate, modern football minimises the working-class prevalence with the middle-class population at 81% (Kleomanis, 2005). On that note, interviewees expressed this shift in demographic towards minimal organised violence. For example, interviewees paralleled modern violence as “People fight over emotion” (A1) and “It’s not structured like before” (A2). Gumusgul and Acet (2016) similarly finds minimal concern for organised violence within modern football matches. Consequently, while violence is minimal interviewees noted a shift towards “Threats at rivals, swearing and maybe throwing something at them” (A5). On that note, hooligan violence has transcended from an organised affair towards spontaneous aggression highlighted by verbal humiliation.

Chapter 5: Findings and Discussion – Media Representation and Policing Sentiments

5.1: Introduction

This chapter examines the interviewees account concerning media representation and football policing. Firstly, the interviewees perception of media representation is investigated. Secondly, the sentiments of marginalisation from media representation are investigated. Thirdly, the interviewees perceptions of football policing and policing culture are investigated. Lastly, interviewees address their desired security strategy in football.

5.2: Media Misrepresentation

Hooligans often directed non-conformist sentiments towards media publications, illustrating a negative relationship (Newson, 2017). These non-conformist sentiments contribute towards the marginalisation of hooligans and a dislike towards media publications. Interviewees liken this sentiment with a unanimous animosity against media publications.

“I don’t think I’ve ever met a lad who likes the media or would even speak to a journalist”.

(A6)

Consistently, participants likened media misrepresentation towards the depiction of firms as a folk devil.

“My parents never visited a football game but always read news regarding football and football violence”. (A5)

Interviewees perspectives parallels academic literature, demonstrating that media misrepresentation fosters a climate of moral panic against hooligans (Martinez, 2016). Interviewees condemned media misrepresentation noting it's influence in contributing to a misunderstanding of hooliganism. Notably, interviewees exclaim that "People don't understand why this makes us happy" (A2). This establishes the phenomenon of hooliganism as a mass media creation rather than an authentic societal threat (Guilianotti, 1994).

Consequently, media misrepresentation denounces the democratic discourse of the hooligan community. Interviewees specifics that "Nobody cares what we have to say" (A5) and "They don't know who we are" (A1). This becomes clear as non-academics and academics commonly explain hooliganism, rather than hooligan's themselves (Chatterjee, 2011). This equalises the hooligans identity towards voicelessness, whereby football policing is shaped by narratives besides their influence.

5.3: Marginalisation

Interviewees recognised that media misrepresentation pushes the marginalisation of their identity. Particularly, interviewees mention that policing measures target hooligans aggressively.

"The police have always demonised us and oppressed us, they only look after the rich and those with money". (A6)

Most interviewees expressed that football policing overtly targets those who resemble a hooligan. Hooligans are often identified through brands such as "Stone Island and CP Company" (A5). Consequently, "If you resemble a hooligan then the police will target you more" (A5). Concerning the hooligan working-class origins, interviewees judged policing as benefiting solely the rich. To explain,

concerning the Glazer protest, interviewee A6 affirms that “It’s funny that they want to protect a horrible c*nt billionaire, but not people paying their taxes”. This marginalisation compounds a hooligan’s psychosocial outlook, whereby viewing themselves as a minority (Gumusgul and Acet, 2016).

Interviewee A6 believed the demonisation of his identity exceeds the demonization of other criminals.

“Murderers and podophiles weren’t looked that down upon as we were”. (A6)

Henceforth, this disproportionate outlook facilitates a bitterness towards authority figures and football policing.

5.4: Policing Sentiments

As noted previously, interviewees disclosed a significant animosity regarding football policing. Practically, Scott et al (2008) hypothesises that amplified deterrence raises the probability of hooligan violence. Several interviewees readdressed the harmful association between football policing and hooligan sentiments.

“I’m not the biggest fan of the police. Anyone who has been in a firm can tell you” (A6)

“I’ve never really felt protected by the police” (A5)

Additionally, the interviewees attributed their working-class heritage amongst influencing their ideology against authority figures.

“I grew up in a working-class area, we were taught to have a disliking to the government and the police”. (A6)

To explain, the working-class heritage advances an environment of violence, which counter-acts ideologies imposed by policing (Guilianotti, 1994). Consequently, this counterbalance inevitably resists the authority of policing, thereby reinforcing ‘us vs them’ narratives. Hooligan literature has identified circumstances where working-class aggressiveness is self-regulated, noting that aggression displaces by itself (Spaaij, 2008). More broadly, empirical analysis by Rennwald and Pontusson (2022) reveals that working-class backgrounds exhibit heightened negative sentiments towards government institutions and authority figures. Henceforth, interviewees and academic studies draw significant separation between hooligans and policing authority, in essence, hooligans perceive policing as the degradation of football. This degradation encompassing the over targeting of hooligans within football matches and in social events (Piskurek, 2008). The Euro 2000 demonstrates this over-targeting, where 965 English fans were arrested while only 1 was convicted for offences (Scott et al., 2008). Accordingly, interviewees depict the imbalance of their identity in policing.

“People are being killed in London every day, but they want to spend their time making sure football fans don’t shout abuse at each other”. (A5)

5.5: Policing Recommendations

Established by their pre-existing experiences with authority figures, the interviewees endorsed minimising policing deterrence within football games. Based on Scott et al (2008) analysis, elevated deterrence pushes emotional arousal within passionate supporters. Interviewees similarly reiterate experiencing marginalisation from football policing, whereby triggering emotions of anger and

frustration. Consequently, Poutvaara and Priks (2009) research expresses the consequential impact of discriminatory practise in heightening hooligan violence. On that note, interviewees supported narratives of minimising policing influence.

“I don’t think sport should be policed so heavily”. (A5)

“It’s clear that the police have no clue what football is and that’s what makes it worse”. (A6)

The interviewees undeniably characterised a notable detachment between policing and football hooligans. To explain, English fans expressed that French policing measures “Didn’t seem appropriate”, as firing tear gas incited further violence (Boffey, 2016). Similarly, interviewee A6 likens his policing mistrust towards the Hillsborough tragedy, in which 97 devoted football fans died. The interviewee insists that Hillsborough occurred “Because of the police” and the fan blaming was “Disgusting” (A6). Interviewee A6 perspective parallels literature uncovering that unfair attitude towards policing functions as perceiving the police as oppressive (Poulton, 2005). Consequently, interviewees demonstrate the ideology of viewing policing authorities as oppressive to self-identified hooligans.

In contrast, interviewees displayed positive discourse concerning football stewards. To explain, stewards diminished issues that are often associated against police officers. On that note, interviewees frame a stable relationship between football fans and football stewards.

“Stewards around the stadium and in the game aren’t bad”. (A2)

These perspectives broadly support Stott et al (2008), who viewed that adopting low-profile policing advances the perceived legitimacy of protective measures within football matches. The interviewees paralleled the stewards as “Fans just like us” (A2), whereby minimises the ‘us vs them’ narrative plaguing policing sentiments. Contrastingly, interviewee A6 likens the police towards having “No clue what football culture is”. Evidently, ideological disparities are apparent between perspectives of football stewards and football policing. Likewise, pre-existing literature discloses the utility of minimal police intervention in controlling aggressive football crowds (Strang et al., 2008). Arguably, interviewees vocalised fondness towards the heightening of stewards within football grounds and minimised policing deterrence. Consequently, Spaaij (2006) raises the importance of readdressing security personnel alongside heightening training (Yusoff, 2015).

5.6: Conclusion

The interviewees vocalised negative attitudes concerning media representation and policing practises. Firstly, media misrepresentation advances the folk devil narrative that plagues the hooligan identity. Martinez (2016) supports the interviewees sentiments, observing that media-misrepresentation provides the catalyst for negativity against hooligan firms. Secondly, interviewees mentioned the marginalisation from media-misrepresentation contributes towards football policing. To explain, interviewees paralleled their policing dislike regarding an excessive focus on their identity. Case in point, interviewees communicated that “Im not the biggest fan of the police” (A6) and “I’ve never really felt protected by the police” (A5). Interviewee A5 similarly mentions that clothing such as “Stone Island and CP company” promotes individuals as a greater target from policing. Consequently, academic literature expresses that excessive deterrence upon hooligan firms assists in facilitating aggressive emotions from marginalisation (Piskurek, 2008).

Thirdly, the interviewees working-class background gradually aided their anti-authoritarian ideology. To explain, interviewee A6 discourses that “I grew up in a working-class area” and “we were taught to have a disliking for the government”. Academic studies disclose that working-class individuals display minimal political engagement, attributing to perceptions of political mistrust (Walsh, Jennings, and Stoker, 2004). On that note, these perspectives undertone narratives favouring football stewards over policing. Interviewees associated football stewards as “Fans just like us” (A2), which minimises narratives of ‘us vs them’ that plagues policing sentiments. Academic literature favours minimal police intervention, whereby minimal deterrence heightens self-regulation of aggressive crowds (Strang et al., 2008). To note, the Euro 2000 represents the contradictory impact of target hardening, evidenced by the apprehension of 956 English fans with only 1 conviction (Scott et al., 2008). Henceforth, the marginalisation of hooligans through policing practices encourages heightening football stewards.

5.7: Study Limitation

The studies limitations concern the chosen methodology. Firstly, while purposeful sampling grants information rich participants, the generalisability of results are limited (Coyne, 1997). While concerns are minimal when generalising English hooligans, concerns arise once generalising European hooligans. To explain, European and English hooligans are vastly different in culture and ideology (Davis, 2022). Secondly, including interviews from law enforcement, football club representatives and the Football Association would offer added breath to the research findings. Thirdly, Spaaij (2008) materialises the reconstruction of hooliganism as it has “Evolved into a persistent transnational subculture” (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016, p.10). Consequently, a longitudinal study would seem more appropriate, where participants are followed over a period of time (Caruana et al., 2015). This would ensure the usability of results over a greater span of time in

England. Despite this, the dissertation findings can serve as a durable motivator for potential research into the relationship between hooliganism and football violence.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

In conclusion, the dissertation aimed to attain a greater understanding of hooliganism and hooligan violence. Thus, this robust comprehension was obtained through investigating several research questions. This dissertation positions that hooliganism and hooligan violence originate from several interconnected determinants, including group bonding, masculine working-class origins, football team alliance and anti-policing ideologies. Contrasting scholarly literature, hooligans accredited minimal significance to alcohol itself directing hooliganism and hooligan violence, rather regarding it as a secondary product of the aforementioned themes. Similarly, excitement develops as an outcome of the aforementioned themes rather than encouraging hooliganism itself. Henceforth, Figure 4 illustrates the interconnected themes referenced from the interviews, excluding alcohol consumption and excitement for anti-policing ideologies. These themes present a complex interrelationship, whereby each determinant interacts symbiotically, therefore strengthening their combined influence. These conclusions parallel Meij et al (2015), specifying hooliganism as a complex multifaceted phenomenon. Consequently, the multifaceted nature of hooliganism renders a comprehensive image of hooligan's challenging. Nevertheless, the research questions grant a valuable framework in comprehending the hooligan identity and hooligan violence.

Figure 4: Illustration of the interconnected themes extracted from the hooligan interview

Firstly, regarding the question ‘What are the most important factors that contribute towards a hooligan identity?’, various influences were uncovered. Fundamentally, the desire for belonging, community, and friendship underscored hooligan firm affiliation. To explain, group belonging fuels the desire for companionship amongst like-minded individuals and hooligans. This parallels wider literature, acknowledging that hooligans perceive their football team as the basis of family, friendship, and community (Guilianotti, 1994). Frequent media misrepresentation marginalises hooligans, cultivating a tightknit social identification within hooligan firms. Stemming from marginalisation, hooligans regularly framed their team as a familial entity, constituted by sentiments of happiness, sadness, passion, and joy. These observations complement broader scholarly literature, recognising the unifying community spirit displayed by hooligan firms (Meij et al., 2015). However, these collective friendships develop a framework that intertwines friendship alongside territorial dominance. For example, defending friendships and club honour often translates into unified violence against rival opposition. To illustrate, West Ham hooligans highlight that

safeguarding their “Territory in the East End of London” served as a consequential impetus for hooligan affiliation (Spaaij, 2008, p.15). Moreover, these tightknit attachments are enhanced by pregame drinking, whereby like-minded individuals foster deep connections. To note, the practice of humiliating chants during pre-game drinking conduces the solidification of individual in a firm and the wider football community, while reinforcing hatred towards rivals. This perception of collective identification slowly nurtures an individual’s introduction and integration within hooligan firms. Consequently, this dissertation demonstrates the sense of belonging, community, ‘and friendship as the greatest motivator for hooligan affiliation.

Secondly, regarding the question ‘To what extent does group interaction and friendship contribute towards violence?’, hooligans recognised a symbiotic association between friendship and violence. Friendships provide the catalyst for membership in hooligan firms and subsequent hooligan violence (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016). Likewise, heightened emotions between rigid hooligan firms during game attendance often affirms the condition for aggressive hooligan tendencies. To explain, goal celebrations repeatedly encompass collective rival humiliation, potentially providing an impetus for spontaneous football violence. Scholarly papers illustrate the interrelationship of hooligan friendships and aggression, whereby friendship nurtures aggression and aggression nurtures friendship (Meij et al., 2015). The masculine-working class identity further demonstrates a nexus amongst violence and friendship dynamics. The working-class culture of quasi-violence parallels violence and friendship, whereby violence functions as solidifying collective bonds (Finn, 2019). On that note, strengthening hooligan friendships benefits hooligan firms within social hierarchies. Tightknit masculine bonds facilitate the manifestation of aggression and strength, exemplified by the intoxicating relationship between Feyenoord and Ajax hooligans (Spaaij, 2008). Thereupon, this dissertation illustrates the capacity of hooligan friendships and interactions in forming the structure that supports football violence.

Thirdly, regarding 'What types of violence and aggression are hooligans involved with?', hooligans acknowledged a shift in violent actions. Historically, violence concerned organised group violence amongst firms; however, contemporary hooliganism minimises structure, favouring verbal aggression and spontaneous violence (Gumusgul and Acet, 2016). This transition is explained by interviewee (A1), recognising that "The old schools hooligans are dead", indicating the death of traditional customs alongside the hooligans. Contemporary violence primarily arises from emotions, as validated by the Manchester United fight against Manchester City fans after their FA Cup Final loss (Andrews, 2023). The organised structured recognised in historical firms is absent in contemporary football, hence advancing the minimal structure of contemporary hooligan violence (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016). Broader territorial possessiveness similarly advances the impetus for spontaneous violence during rival derby days. Consequently, rival fans are regularly separated to minimise spontaneous violence; regardless, verbal humiliation prevails. Contemporary hooligan violence is characterised by intense hostility, this hostility materialises and authorises both verbal onslaught and spontaneous act of violence towards rival fans. Paralleling scholarly literature, collective football hatred legitimises violence against rival oppositions (Strang et al., 2018). As such, this dissertation illustrates that contemporary hooligan violence encircles verbal aggression and spontaneous violence, arising from rival confrontation, emotional arousal, and significant hostility.

Lastly, regarding the question 'To what extent, positively or negatively do hooligans perceive football policing and what alternatives do they prefer?', overwhelming hostile sentiments were acknowledged. Heightened deterrence during football matches increases hooligan emotional output, whereby developing the likelihood of spontaneous football violence (Scott et al., 2008). This dissertation similarly observed mistrust between football policing and hooligan firms. For example, hooligans regarded the Hillsborough disaster as a fundamental source towards their hostility towards football policing. Consequently, this perspective underscores an evident 'us vs them' framework between hooligans and football policing. The Euro 2000 grounds this intoxicating

relationship, contrasting the arrest of 965 English fans with only 1 conviction (Scott et al., 2008). This over-representation in arrest influenced robust support for minimising policing and increasing football stewards. Scholarly literature parallels advocacy for minimal policing, detecting self-regulation within aggressive crowds during football matches (Strang et al., 2008). Accordingly, hooligans recognised football stewards as similar football fans, whereby minimising the negative narratives of 'us vs them'. The minimal hatred focused on football stewards position their suitability more favourably in maintaining order than football policing. This approach minimises the classical working-class aggression towards football policing while heightening self-regulation during emotional games (Strang et al., 2008). Thereupon, this dissertation illustrates the hostile sentiments towards football policing, influence on football violence and the advocacy for minimised deterrence.

Conversely, this dissertation has illustrated the multifaceted nature of football hooliganism and hooligan violence. The findings delegate that hooliganism and hooligan violence arise from social bonding, masculine working-class origins, football team alliance and anti-policing ideologies. This dissertation provides several positive academic implications by analysing hooliganism within the perspective of the most combative clubs in 2022/2023 (GOV, 2023). Consequently, this paper contributes a valuable lens to comprehend hooliganism in modern football within England. However, hooliganism is an "Evolved" phenomenon, manipulated by considerable changes overtime (Cleland and Cashmore, 2016, p.10). Therefore, the effort to comprehend hooliganism and hooligan violence remains one that lacks an accurate conclusion. There exist opportunities to expand past this dissertation by encompassing discourse from various stakeholders, including law enforcement, representatives within the Football Association, and football journalists. Similarly, incorporating the perspective of European ultras can provide a greater comprehension of the hooligan identity and the framework for violence.

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